

Correlational Analysis of Sports Preferences and Mathematical Interests

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between those interested in math and the preferred sports they play using a survey. Participants had to answer which types of math they were interested in and indicate the sport or sports they engage in, and the option to state where they reside. The study aimed to see if there is a correlation between those who enjoy math and rock climbing. Preliminary observations suggest that those who enjoy math are more likely to select rock climbing as a sport, prompting an investigation into this potential connection.

I. Introduction

Researchers have historically been keen on the association between professionals and their personal hobbies, as these activities can reflect one's cognitive processes and characteristics pertaining to one's occupation. While sports and exercise are crucial to maintaining a healthy lifestyle, their correlation in mathematics is less well understood.

This study aims to explore whether there is a significant preference for rock climbing among individuals with a strong interest in mathematics compared to other sports. By examining and potentially confirming a correlation, the question of whether one's occupation aligns with their personal interest can offer a broader insight and expand on various professions and the activities individuals enjoy in their times of leisure.

It is hypothesized that there is a significant preference for rock climbing among those interested in math compared to other sports. This hypothesis will be tested by using and analyzing survey responses from those interested in mathematics and

their sports preferences. Inferences can be made as to why those with mathematical interests enjoy rock climbing. Dopamine could be the culprit. Dopamine, often referred to as the 'feel-good' neurotransmitter, releases feelings of pleasure and satisfaction. Berridge (2017) explains that the nucleus accumbens, located in the lower front of the brain, is critical for processing feelings of motivation, pleasure, and reward (para. 10). Berridge's extensive research highlights the significance of the nucleus accumbens and its connection to dopamine, reinforcing feelings of achievement.

Mathematics is always evolving, requiring professionals to adapt to constant development and challenges. Such an example is solving the over 160-year-old unsolved mathematical conjecture, the Riemann hypothesis. Similarly, rock climbing can be compared to those interested in mathematics with the need to improve. Naylor (2023) found that rock climbers often aim for improvement not just in their climbing technique, but also in areas such as gear development, the history of the sport, and their interactions within the climbing community (p. 32). This commitment could parallel those who enjoy

mathematics. The American Mathematical Society supports these pursuits by hosting meetings, events, and collaborations among mathematicians. With The American Mathematical Society encouraging these interests, those who have taken a liking to mathematics could be reflected as well.

II. Methodology

A total of 23 participant responses were collected. This sample was gathered by sharing a survey form over the span of three weeks using social media platforms to achieve an opportunity sample. The criteria were that the individuals filling out the form had to be interested in math, and no specific age range was recorded. Participants were not required to answer the last question, which asked where they currently reside. The question was indicated to participants that it was for demographic purposes only and to explore any potential variations based on their location. The preferred sport was operationalized as “enjoy and currently participate in or have experience with”. The type of mathematics ranged from Algebra to Topology, and participants were given a choice of ‘other’ to explain another region of mathematics that they were interested in. The same applied for sports, giving participants the option to list other sports.

The way data was collected was through a survey with closed-ended, open-ended, and checkmark responses. Participants could select multiple sports and the math they were interested in, and if they happened to not play a sport or have experience with one, they must indicate so in ‘Other’. The participants were instructed to complete a short form that contained five questions in a quiet and well-lit room. They were also notified that completing the form would take five minutes or less. Participants were noted that the place they resided was optional and for demographic purposes, and that their responses would be kept confidential. Ultimately, participants were asked these questions

in order: their name, the type of mathematics they are interested in, the sports they have participated in or are currently in, and the optional question of what country or state they are in.

The questions addressed the following: the type of math they are interested in to see if there could be a correlation to the involvement of sport(s) they participate in, the sport(s) they are currently involved in to confirm the hypothesis, and the optional demographic-based question to see if there is a link between other sports preferences vary on where one lives.

Ethics were held and were taken caution of by ensuring informed consent from the participants. Confidentiality was emphasized as well using anonymous data collection.

III. Results

According to participant responses, there was a range of sports that they engaged in. With common sports such as running were frequently reported, some participants took part in combat sports such as martial arts and water-based sports like kayaking. The measure of spread in the number of sports participants partook in showed a mean of 1.78 and a median of 1, with the ‘other’ category including a variety of less commonly played sports. These results show that there is a diverse number of sports that participants played. Most participant responses reported residing in North America, Europe, and Asia as well. This could indicate that the sports played varied by region where the participants were.

Regarding mathematical interests, 60.9% of participants indicated a preference for Statistics, making it the most preferred topic in mathematics.

The list followed with 52.2% being interested in Algebra, and 56.5% interested in Geometry. Notably, some concepts had similar levels of interest. For example, 30.7% of participants preferred Calculus and Differential Equations, while Applied Mathematics was selected by 26%. Topology and Pure Mathematics were tied at 21.7%, and 17.4% of participants chose Number Theory.

As shown in Figure 1, a pie chart was used to interpret the results more easily. Most participants selected running, with only one participant selecting 'N/A'. This visual aid assists us in understanding the proportions of what sport was preferred the most.

The distribution of mathematical interests and sports can indicate interesting trends. One such instance is the interest in Statistics, and how participants could suggest a potential broader trend in data-related topics. The variety in sports could also reflect demographic differences within the participants. Overall, mathematical interests could reflect what sport the individual plays. Future research could be conducted and explore a correlation between sports preferences and mathematical interests more deeply, and how the sport can influence certain mathematical problem-solving skills.

It is crucial to acknowledge that this data was based on participants being able to self-report the sports they play, the math they are interested in, and where they live. This could indicate a potential bias or inaccuracy. The sample size was relatively small as well, so generalization may be limited. Future studies can include a larger sample and more diverse groups of participants to explore this correlation more in-depth.

Figure 1. Pie chart of preferred sports preferences

IV. Discussion

The study originally aimed to explore a potential correlation between those interested in mathematics and rock climbing. However, results reveal that there is no correlation between the two. With 20.8% of the participants selecting running compared to 10.4% of participants engaging in rock climbing, it was placed as the third most popular preferred sport to select. The hypothesis was disproven.

An intriguing aspect of the study for potential ideas that can be open to discussion is the topic of mathematics that the participants chose. With, 60.9% of participants selecting statistics as their interest, the prominence of statistics could indicate a broader trend or preference within the population sampled, potentially influencing how individuals engage with various activities, including rock climbing. Although no correlation is present, these results may warrant further exploration if another study is made. The sample size could have been varied with more participants, opening to different responses and possibly making a stronger connection. There has been no proven correlation to sports for this study.

A limitation of this research was the lack of material connecting mathematical interests with sports preferences. Two relevant references were found, indicating that there may be a gap on this topic. Further research on this subject can lead to a better understanding of the correlation between people's interests and the sports they play. These results do not have to apply to those who are interested in mathematics or professions in the mathematical field, but they could also apply to careers, in general, to see if a certain career leads to a preferred sport. A potential relationship between interest in different jobs and skills. Future research could benefit from examining a larger and more varied sample to enhance findings.

Despite the study not being able to find a significant correlation between mathematical interests and rock climbing, the high level of interest in Statistics among participants highlights the need for further exploration into how specific mathematical disciplines might influence engagement in various activities. Overall, this study contributes to an ongoing exploration of how intellectual and athletic pursuits intersect.

V. Implications

The findings of this study, despite disproving the initial hypothesis of a correlation between mathematical interests and rock climbing, the study offers significant insights into the relationship between intellectual pursuits and athletic activities. With 20.8% of participants preferring to run, along with cycling and soccer tied with 12.5%, only 10.4% engaged in rock climbing, placing rock climbing as the third most popular sport. Once again, this result indicates that while no direct correlation was found between mathematical interests and rock climbing, the data may still offer valuable perspectives on broader trends.

Future studies could build on these findings by exploring how other mathematical topics—such as Algebra II, Calculus III, or Number Theory—might influence participation in different sports or physical activities. Perhaps being more specific on which types of Algebra or Calculus could yield descriptive results.

Moreover, the findings could have practical implications for educational and career guidance. Understanding how intellectual interests and athletic preferences may aid educators and career advisors in providing more tailored recommendations for others. School-wise, integrating interests in mathematics with extracurricular activities that align with cognitive strengths could offer students more holistic development opportunities and a chance to explore what they would like to pursue academically.

In summary, while this study did not find a significant correlation between mathematical interests and rock climbing, the high level of interest in Statistics among participants suggests potential areas for further exploration. Expanding this research could enhance our understanding of how intellectual and physical pursuits intersect and inform practices in education and career development.

VI. Conclusion

In conclusion, while the conducted study disproved of the initial hypothesis, this correlational research further opens a new field to explore an intersection between one's intellectual pursuits and the athletic activities they partake in.

The data suggests that psychological or cognitive traits influence both mathematical interests and sports preferences, making a base to delve more into different inquiries and expand these connections. Moreover, considering demographics such as culture offers insight into how the

environment shapes intellectual interests and athletic preferences.

This research offers a deeper understanding of the relationship between cognitive and physical pursuits, contributing to a more comprehensive exploration of human behavior.

VII. References

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